

Ukrainian Conference
with International Participation

CHEMISTRY, PHYSICS AND TECHNOLOGY OF SURFACE

devoted to
40th anniversary of the
Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry
of NAS of Ukraine

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Тези доповідей Всеукраїнської конференції з міжнародною участю “Хімія, фізика і технологія поверхні”, присвяченій 40-річчю з дня заснування Інституту хімії поверхні ім. О.О. Чуйка НАН України – Київ, 2026. – 290 с.

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Збірник містить тези доповідей, які було представлено на конференції. Тематика конференції: теорія хімічної будови та реакційна здатність поверхні твердих тіл; фізико-хімія поверхневих та міжфазних явищ; хімія, фізика та технологія наноматеріалів; медико-біологічні та біохімічні аспекти вивчення наноматеріалів. Тези доповідей подано в авторській редакції.

The Book contains abstracts of the Conference presentations. The Conference topics: theory of chemical structure and reactivity of solid surfaces; physical chemistry of surface and interfacial phenomena; chemistry, physics and technology of nanomaterials; medical, biological and biochemical aspects of investigation of nanomaterials. The abstracts are published in the author's edition.

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Influence of nanoscale structure on the microwave properties of MgTiO₃ ceramics

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The rapid development of 5G telecommunication systems (Frequency Range 3) requires new dielectric materials with low dielectric constant (ϵ_r), high quality factor ($Q \cdot f$), and thermal stability [1,2]. Magnesium titanate (MgTiO₃) is a promising candidate, but traditional solid-state synthesis requires high temperatures (1650 °C). In this work, we present the synthesis of MgTiO₃ nanoparticles using the Pechini method and investigate their structural and microwave properties.

The synthesis involved the use of citric acid as a chelating agent and ethylene glycol as a polymerizing agent. TEM and SEM analysis confirmed the formation of a nanocrystalline structure with crystallite sizes ranging from 20 to 40 nm after calcination at 650 °C. Increasing the annealing temperature led to a controlled growth of nanoparticles from 50 nm (800 °C) to 80 nm (900 °C). XRD analysis confirmed the synthesis of high-purity geikielite with a rhombohedral unit cell.

The use of nanosized powders allowed for a significant reduction in the sintering temperature to 1400 °C (by 250 °C compared to traditional routes). The resulting ceramics exhibited a relative dielectric constant $\epsilon_r \approx 17$ and an exceptional quality factor $Q \cdot f$ ranging from 54,500 to 97,000 GHz at 10 GHz. The temperature coefficient of resonance frequency τ_f was measured at -50 ppm/°C. These results demonstrate the high efficiency of the Pechini route for producing energy-efficient, high-performance microwave dielectrics.

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